

**VOLUME-2
ISSUE-4**

**ISSN : 2271-4864
NOVEMBER/2014**

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN MANAGEMENT STUDIES

AN INTERNATIONALLY APPROVED AND PEER-REVIEWED JOURNAL

**Chief Editor
Dr.N.V.S.Suryanarayana**

Invited Articles from:-

**BANKING, BRAND MANAGEMENT, BUSINESS ADMINISTRATION, FINANCE, BIOTECHNOLOGY
BUSINESS MANAGEMENT, CLINICAL RESEARCH, CONSTRUCTION MANAGEMENT,
ECONOMICS, FASHION DESIGNING, HEALTH CARE, HOSPITAL ADMINISTRATION, MLM,
HOSPITALITY MANAGEMENT, HOTEL MANAGEMENT, HUMAN RESOURCES (HR),
INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY, INFRASTRUCTURE MANAGEMENT, RETAIL MANAGEMENT
INTERNATIONAL BUSINESS, LOGISTICS, MARKETING, MATERIALS MANAGEMENT,
OIL & GAS, OPERATIONS MANAGEMENT, PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT, MEDIA SERVICES,
PETROLEUM STUDIES, PHARMA, PUBLIC RELATIONS, REAL ESTATE, TELECOMMUNICATIONS,
INSURANCE & RISK MANAGEMENT, RURAL MANAGEMENT, PSYCHOLOGY, INTERNATIONAL,
BUSINESS, PERSONALITY DEVELOPMENT, COMMUNICATION SCIENCE, AND RELATED AREAS.**

**WESTWIND PUBLISHING HOUSE
FLAT NO 109/8, ANITHA NAGAR, LOWKHANDWALA COMPLEX
KHANDAVILLI EAST, MUMBAI, MAHARASTRA, INDIA**

FOR SUBSCRIPTION OF ARTICLES AND QUERIES :

DR.N.V.S.SURYANARAYANA

CHIEF EDITOR

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN MANAGEMENT STUDIES (IJRMS)

**DOOR.NO.19-5-5, KANUKURTHIVARI STREET,
VIZIANAGARAM - 535002, ANDHRA PRADESH, INDIA**

E-MAIL : ijmr09@gmail.com, ijpe999@gmail.com

PHONE : 09666633885, 09440348609

ISSN-2321-4864

ISSN-2321-4864

**MANAGEMENT EDUCATION AND DEVELOPMENT ISSUES, CHALLENGES
AND STRATEGIES: AN ANALYSIS AND REVIEW**

*** DR. P. SANJEEVI**

Abstract:

This paper examines the proposition that action learning is a new model in Traditional Management Education. Action learning is becoming widely accepted methodology for the development of managers and managerial competence. This is in both public and private sector organizations and within the context of certificated and organizationally based programmes. Traditional Management Education and Development characteristics level of formal education, frequency of management training, specificity of strategic management education, and time elapsed since formal education drive adoption of strategy tools. Specifically, these features spotlight to management. From this a framework is developed that compares a traditional approach to management education with an action learning approach in all levels of management. Our findings are that action learning is a new paradigm, but for the maximum benefit to be gained from the approach its application needs to be more carefully considered, particularly in relation to the provision of some wider peripheral frameworks for the manager to use as 'tools for thinking'. We conclude with a predictive model of the relative importance of management education and development is highlighted with demographic characteristics on strategy tool adoption.

Key words: *Strategic Tools, Management Education, Traditional Management*

Introduction:

Traditional education is associated with much stronger elements of coercion than seems to be acceptable in most cultures now. It has sometimes included: the use of corporal punishment to maintain classroom discipline or punish errors; inculcating the dominant religion and language; separating students according to gender, race, and social class, as well as teaching different subjects to girls and boys. In terms of curriculum there was still a high level of attention paid to time-honored academic knowledge. At present times it varies enormously from culture to culture, but still tends to be characterized by a much higher level of coercion than alternative education. Traditional schooling in Britain, its possessions and former colonies tends to follow the English Public School style of strictly enforced uniforms and a militaristic style of discipline. This can be contrasted with South African, USA and Australian schools, which has a much higher tolerance for spontaneous student-to-teacher communication

In India, management education has been prompting since 1990s, which has resulted in a rapid growth of Management Colleges and Business Schools offering the management programmes both at graduate & undergraduate levels. This is in both public and private sector organizations and within the context of certificated and organizationally based programmes. Traditional Management Education and Development in India the main characteristics are level of formal education, frequency of management training, specificity of strategic management education, and time elapsed since formal education and drive adoption of strategy tools. Specifically, these features spotlight to management. It is observed that Indian Management education is struggling hard to introduce several adaptations because of differences in the work culture system. That made Indian Business education to face several issues in the field of academics, development of infrastructure & financial support. The Govt. of India had also appointed various committees to take a critical review & the overall growth of Business Education in the country. Owing to the intense competition at the global level lot of changes are

taking place in the industries. In turn there is a need to make the changes in the business education system all over the world. India is no exception to it; but the pace is very slow. Now time has come to take a detailed review and to investigate the various challenges & issues which are being faced by these management institutions for enhancing the quality of management education in the country.

The definition of traditional education varies greatly with geography and by historical period. The chief business of traditional education is to transmit to a next generation those skills, facts, and standards of moral and social conduct to the next generations that adults deem to be necessary for their material and social success. As beneficiaries of this scheme, which educational progressively described a John Dewey's being, "imposed from above and from outside", the students are expected to docilely and obediently receive and believe these fixed answers. Teachers are the instruments by which this knowledge is communicated and these standards of behavior are enforced.

Objectives of the Study :

Main objectives of the study are as follows:

- To know the historical evolution, growth and development of management education in India
- To observe strategy tool is an important source to the management education in India
- To identify the management education major issues and challenges.

Research Hypotheses For analyzing the objectives of the study, the following hypotheses are to be tested.

H₁: Strategy is a tool to the management education in India.

H₂: There is no difference between Traditional Management Education and Modern Management Education.

Methodology:

Data Collection:

The data was collected from primary and secondary source of data. Primary data was collected through interview and questionnaire method. The researchers contacted many management colleges, students, B schools and explained the purpose of the study. The present paper is based on descriptive mainly on secondary data. This data has been collected from various authentic sources such as AICTE Hand Book year 2011-12, India today Reports, websites, management magazines and other management survey reports.

Present Structure of Indian Management Education

Present Structure Management Education in India is divided into six categories.

- Indian Institute of Management (IIMs) was setup by government of India.
- University Departments of Management studies, distance, correspondence & part time courses as well.
- Colleges & Institutes affiliated to universities.
- Private or Govt. Institutes approved by All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE).

- Private Institutes or colleges not affiliated to any universities are not approved by AICTE.
- Private colleges or Institutes are offering MBA courses in India in collaboration with foreign universities where degree & diploma certificates are awarded by the foreign universities.

In present days, learning has become students centric. Branding has accelerated the management education. Top Management Schools are continuously changing the contents & delivery modes. It is equally imperative to Indian Management Schools to strive continuously to make management education context specific. But the present proliferation of Management Schools raises a serious question on the quality of management education. When will this proliferation of Management Schools leave the country? What will be the quality of managers which are produced by these Management Schools. This sudden proliferation has led to a considerable decline in the quality of management education.

Growth of Management Institutions in India			
Year	Management Institutions	Growth	Growth Rate (%)
2006-07	1132	-	-
2007-08	1149	17	2%
2008-09	1523	374	33%
2009-10	1940	417	27%
2010-11	2262	322	17%
2011-12	2385	123	5%
2012-13	2467	82	3%

Source: Annual Reports of AICTE

The percentage growth in number of management institutions in India have come down from high of 33% in 2008-09 (academic year) to 3% in 2012-13. This translates into slowdown growth in starting of new institutions from 417 in 2009-09 to 82 in 2012-13. In terms of absolute numbers, the number of new management schools declined from 417 in 2009-10 to 82 in 2012-13.

This decline is a combination of two primary factors--weak regulatory mechanisms and profit motives of some private players. During the years of high growth in management institutions corruption in regulatory authorities was also rising high and many institutions were approved by overlooking qualitative deficiencies for bribes. At the same time, many private players were rushing into education "business" as a low-risk high cash-flow business with an opportunity to leverage on real-estate (another sector plagued with tax-evaded "black money") and tax-free status of pseudo-non-profits. This opened the floodgates of many private institutions which compromised quality to save money on soft and hard infrastructure. And hence students graduating from these institutions were unemployable (of course, the recession did not help either) which in turn created negative word of mouth for institutions to get future student enrollment. Given that private institutions rely solely on tuition for revenue, lack of enrollment means financial instability. As a result, a large number of management institutions

are now facing problems of vacant seats and are even available for sale. This in turn has slowed the growth of new institutions. Although the growth of engineering and management institutions has slowed down, with 2,500 management schools, India has disproportionately large number of institutions, indicating high value Indians place of job-oriented, professional programs with social prestige

Table - 2

State-wise distribution of Business Schools in India

S. No.	State	No. of Business Schools	Percentage
1	Andhra Pradesh	945	26.57
2	Bihar	16	0.4
3	Delhi	21	0.5
4	Gujarat	131	3.7
5	Haryana	157	4.41
6	Karnataka	209	5.87
7	Kerala	277	7.78
8	Madhya Pradesh	215	6.04
9	Maharashtra	419	11.78
10	Orissa	79	2.22
11	Punjab	186	5.23
12	Rajasthan	134	3.76
13	Tamil Nadu	389	10.93
14	Utar Pradesh	459	12.91
15	Uttarakhand	49	1.37
16	West Bengal	150	4.21
17	Chhatisgarh	27	0.75
18	Jharkhand	8	0.22
19	Himachal Pradesh	13	3.65
20	Jammu and Kashmir	11	3.1
21	Assam	6	0.16
22	Pondicherry	6	0.16
23	Others	2	0.05
	Total	3556	100

* Others: Sikkim and Dadra & Nagar Haveli each have one. Source: AICTE Hand Book, Year 2010-11

List of Business Schools in India

Major Issues:

- Conduct Faculty Development Programs.
- Incorporate Corporate Governance practices in management institutions.
- Need to broaden the specialization.
- Develop reading materials relevant to Indian Context.
- Develop interaction with Industry and Companies.
- Evolve a proper system of Accreditation & Rating.
- Create an Independent Institutional mechanism.
- Ensure Quality Faculty.
- Promote Research Culture.
- Create a global mindset.

Challenges:

Higher education especially in management faculty in India stands at a crossroads. Without any change, the traditional university structure of educating and training tomorrow's business leaders is likely to be surpassed and discarded in the increasingly diverse and technological global economy. To provide our students, we must recognize and accept the challenges before us today.

- All Management Institutions are now trying over for the best of the best managers.
- Well trained and highly resourceful persons.
- Meet the standards to achieve successful human resource management.
- Development of information technology.
- Highlighting the role of soft skills

As a matter of fact the ranking status of the business school of the USA and Asia Pacific is given due to their roles played in producing management experts of the corporations. In the changing scenario of managing, each business has to depend on such a business school to fulfill the required management skill. The business schools those who have poor standing in case of setting right vision statement, have got drawbacks curriculum integration process accordingly

and finally, do not have exposure to effective approaches to offer the programs have been treated as inefficient institutions to the corporate leaders. As the area change is taking place in economic, political and technological environment the world over, new opportunities are opening which are prepared to fight mediocrity and quality in every aspect of life are becoming essential for the survival.

Strategy is a tool for Management Education

This study identified that strategic aspects plays an important role for development of management education in India.

- Strategy through continuous training and development programs for the various levels of managers.
- Mentorship of the newly inducted management trainees.
- Implementing proper ERP models for knowledge sharing among the various functions of the organization so as to enable managers to take effective decisions.
- Continuous acknowledgement of the role of the various employees and managers in the overall organizational development and its achievements.
- Creating effective management development programs to accelerate the emergence of responsible leadership at various levels of management.
- Creating an ethical code of conduct (the company credo) which should promote a culture of ethics and transparency.
- Enact stringent policy measures to counter any possible unethical practice at various levels of the organization.

Testing of Hypotheses

H₁: Strategy is a tool to the Management Education in India.

Opinion of respondents: Strategy is a tool to the Management Education

Table-3

	Students		Faculty		Management	
	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent
Yes	224	75	146	73	74	74
No	76	25	54	27	26	26
Total	300	100	200	100	100	100

Source: Survey

Degree of freedom: (r-1) (c-1) ie. (2-1) (3-1) is 2

Calculated value: 25.65

Table value at 0.05 levels: 1.610

Since the calculated value of Chi-square is less than the table value at 5 percent level of significance, the hypothesis H₀ is accepted and it can be concluded that strategy is a tool to the management education in India.

H₂: There is no difference between Traditional Management Education and Modern Management Education.

Opinion of respondents:

No difference between Traditional Management Education and Modern Management Education

Table-4

	Students		Faculty		Management	
	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent
Yes	43	14	38	19	88	88
No	257	86	162	81	12	12
Total	300	100	200	100	100	100

Source: Survey

Degree of freedom: (r-1) (c-1) ie. (2-1) (3-1) is 2

Calculated value: 0.93

Table value at 0.05 levels: 1.610

Since the calculated value of Chi square is more than the table value at 5 percent level of significance, the hypothesis H₀ is rejected and it can be concluded that there is a difference between Traditional Management Education and Modern Management Education in India.

Suggestions and Conclusion:

It is important for candidates/aspirants before choosing a professional they understand the prerequisites of management education. It is also equally important for the institutions and universities to focus towards quality input, quality education and converting into quality product. Education is not a quantity game; it has never been a number fight neither core course investment business. It needs value addition at all levels and more toward vertical growth than horizontal. Management institutes need to shift from quantity to quality driven. Institutions do not teach the element of professionalism, an important ingredient towards building leading managers. Communications skill for students from rural areas is like climbing the Himalayas.

This study compliments that the India's Management education is undergoing a major change. Firstly, Internationalization, cross cultures, strategic alliances, partnership & mergers are the new trends in management education. Secondly, Indian philosophies have stood valid even after several centuries. On the same lines, adoption of different forms of case study methods in teaching in India since ancient times itself highlights the relevance of Case Studies in Management Education. Further, it is concluded that a predictive model of the relative importance of management education and development is highlighted with demographic characteristics on strategy tool adoption. It is suggested that Indian management institutions have to think in this direction getting these things right is vital for future success.

References:

- Bo wonder & S.L.Rao, Management education in India its evolution & some contemporary issues, AIMA/CME 2005
- Dayal Ishwar, developing management education in India, Journal of management Research, 2, August 2006 P.101
- AICTE Hand Book year 2006-12
- AICTE Annual Reports year 2006-13
- Rao S.L, Report of the working group on management education formed by National Knowledge Committee, 2005.
- Vipin Gupta, Kamala Golakota, Anchors Sreekumar, Quality in Business education: A study of the Indian context, A paper presented at conference held at Atlanta 7th Nov. 2003.
- AACSB International, The value proposition for Business Education, CIME Task Force report; Ethics Education in Business Schools, 2004.
- Ajay Kumar Penthoi & Dr.Sankarashan Dash, Indian Higher Education in the Era of Globalization: Challenges & Quality management strategies, University News, Dec. 2005
- GFM, The Global Management Education Landscape, Shaping the future of Business